

Integrated germplasm improvement—rainfed lowland

IR-Kesar: a brown planthopper (BPH)-resistant variety for Cambodia

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Early rice varieties with duration of less than 120 d are grown during wet season (WS) as normal and August-seeded crops. They are grown during dry season (DS) as water-receding crops, which are seeded from Oct to Jan with no or partial irrigation, and as normal DS crops under full irrigation during Jan-Mar.

Most of the varieties planted are photoperiod-insensitive modern ones, the most popular of which are IR36, IR42, and IR50. During the past 3 yr, IR66,

IR72, and Kru have been spreading quickly. Weakly photoperiod-sensitive traditional varieties are also grown.

BPH is a serious pest during DS and occasionally during WS. Varietal resistances of IR36, IR42, and IR66 are no longer effective against BPH. Kru and IR72 are only the moderately resistant varieties available, thus the need for additional resistant varieties was realized.

Breeding line IR48525-100-1-2 was introduced to Cambodia from IRRI in 1989. The line is a cross of advanced breeding lines IR24632-34-2 and IR31868-64-2-3-3-3. The superior performance of IR48525-100-1-2 was observed in various trials in both DS and WS since 1990 (Table 1). IR48525-100-1-2 yielded as much as IR50, IR66, IR72,

and Kru. Under serious BPH infestation, however, IR48525-100-1-2 outperformed other varieties (Table 2). It also has some resistance to leafhopper, gall midge, and stem borer. IR48525-100-1-2 was named IR-Kesar and recommended for testing at more than 190 locations in Cambodia during 1993. ■

Table 1. Performance of IR-Kesar (IR48525-100-1-2) and checks for seedling vigor, duration, height, BPH damage score, phenotypic acceptability (PAcp), and yield in various trials. Cambodia, 1990-92.

	PYT, ^a 1990 DS (2 locations)		PYT, early ^b 1990 (2 locations)		
	IR-Kesar	IR50	IR-Kesar	IR66	IR72
Vigor	-	-	4.0	6.0	7.0
Duration (d)	116	105	118	110	118
Height (cm)	94	76	93	89	81
PAcp	4.5	5.5	4.5	4.5	4.0
Yield (t/ha)	3.8	3.2	5.3	4.4	4.2

	AYT, ^c 1991 DS (10 locations)		AYT, early 1991 (14 locations)	
	IR-Kesar	Kru	IR-Kesar	Kru
Vigor	2.8	3.0	3.0	3.6
Duration (d)	116	113	115	113
Height (cm)	86	80	87	84
PAcp			2.5	2.5
BPH ^d	1.5	2.2		
Yield (t/ha)	4.74	4.68	4.20	4.46

	AYT, 1992 DS (9 locations)		AYT, early 1992 (17 locations)	
	IR-Kesar	Kru	IR-Kesar	Kru
Vigor	1.8	2.8	3.7	3.7
Duration (d)	114	108	122	114
Height (cm)	88	83	79	78
PAcp	3.0	4.3	3.3	3.6
BPH ^d	0.3	1.5	-	-
Yield (t/ha)	4.37	4.32	2.8	2.7

^aPYT = preliminary yield trial. ^bEarly season = Jan-Mar. ^cAYT = advanced yield trial. ^dScored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

Table 2. Performance of IR-Kesar (IR48525-100-1-2) in advanced yield trial at Prey Phdau (Kampong Speu Province) Research Station under severe BPH infestation. 1991 DS.

Entry	Yield (t/ha)	BPH score ^a (0-9)
IR48525-100-1-2	4.0	1.5
IR48563-123-5-5-2	1.7	6.5
IR48613-21-3-2-2	2.9	2.5
IR50363-8-1-1-3	2.4	7.0
IR50363-61-1-2-2	1.9	6.5
IR51008-89-2-1-2	2.6	3.5
IR51009-58-1-1-2	1.8	5.5
IR52280-64-3-3-3	1.7	6.5
IR52256-203-2-2-3	1.6	6.0
Kru (check)	3.3	2.2
Mean	2.4	4.8

^aScored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

Lioto, a short-duration rice variety suitable for northern Zaire

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Farmers tend to grow maize, peanut, and cotton rather than rice during the first cropping season (Apr-Aug) in Bambesa Zone of northern Zaire to avoid severe damage to the rice crop by birds and big rodents (*Thryonomys swinderianus*) called simbiliki. Rice is grown with fewer problems during the second season (Sep-Dec) when rain is often inadequate. Varieties such as IRAT112 have a short growth duration and are appropriate for late planting during the second season.

IRAT112 (RY150) has been cultivated in Bambesa Zone since 1985 because of its short growth duration (110 d) and